

Gather.Town

Developed by: Gather Presence Inc.

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Keywords

Group Learning, Language, Media Literacy, Online Collaboration, Online Interaction Skills, Remote Teamwork

Figure 1. Screenshot from *Gather.Town* (Gather Presence Inc.). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

Gather.Town is a gamified virtual work environment that supports online learning, virtual conferencing, and remote teamwork. Players create their own customizable avatar to represent themselves and move around in the virtual environment. *Gather.Town* uses proximity-based video and audio chat: when player avatars are physically proximate in the game space, a video chat interface appears, enabling them to talk to each other in real time. This facilitates spontaneous communication and social interaction like in the real world. Featuring custom pixel art, the platform offers templates for office layouts, though the virtual office or classroom is fully customizable depending on the user's payment plan. Other *Gather.Town* features include scheduling, integration with tools such as calendars and email, and built-in minigames and team activities. The virtual environment was designed and

developed by the for-profit company, Gather Presence Inc., with multiple payment options for users, including a free one.

Facts

Release date:	May 2020
Developer:	Gather Presence Inc.
Game type:	Digital, requires an internet connection
Number of players:	Multiplayer
Format:	Hybrid
Time frame:	Any
Languages:	English, Japanese, Portuguese
Environment:	Web browser, desktop app, mobile app
Material:	There is a robust set of tutorials available on Gather's website that instruct users on how to use the virtual environment.
Price:	Free for 10 or fewer users; multiple payment plans available for larger groups.

Resonance & Criticism

Gather.Town gained popularity as a virtual office and classroom during the COVID-19 pandemic (Lu, 2021). The platform was praised for its proximity chat features, customizability, ease of implementation, facilitation of serendipitous interactions between users, and its fun and engaging nature (Lu, 2021; Komar, 2023; Mascarenhas, 2021; McCulloch, 2020). However, Gather.Town was also criticized for requiring users to have a stable internet connection and for potential privacy concerns about the platform's management of user data (Komar, 2023). While most empirical research on Gather.Town is positive, some scholars criticize the short duration of these studies and their reliance on self-reporting (Lo & Song, 2023).

Game Principle & Process

Users must create an account on Gather.Town, which involves choosing a username and optionally uploading a profile picture. Once an account has been created and users are logged in, they will be prompted to create and customize an avatar to represent them in the virtual classroom or office.

On the user's website homepage, referred to as a dashboard, users can see the virtual environments they belong to and click on them to enter. Alternatively, users can create a new virtual classroom or office space from their dashboard. The space owner can use the mapmaker feature to design the virtual classroom, changing its theme, layout, and size. For example, instructors can add, delete, and move rooms, furniture, décor, and other interactive

objects. It is possible to designate certain rooms for specific activities, such as meeting rooms or casual spaces.

After the virtual classroom is created, the space owner can invite students and others via a link or email. A password can also be set for an additional layer of security, and users will be prompted to enter it to gain access to the classroom. Once new users have created an account and designed an avatar, they will enter the classroom. They can “claim a desk,” a feature that allows users to claim a small portion of the room and customize it.

Due to Gather.Town’s proximity chat features, users will only be able to see and hear one another when their avatars are physically close in the virtual classroom. For example, students could be split into groups, and each group could move to different areas of the classroom. They would see and hear their group members' video and audio, since they are proximate, but they would not see or hear other groups. However, there is also a messaging feature, so users can message each other or a group, even if their avatars are not close to one another in the classroom.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Gather.Town’s goal as a platform is to improve online communication, interaction, and collaboration in virtual work, educational, and leisure settings. With features specifically designed to assist in educational endeavors, Gather.Town creates a virtual environment conducive to learning and teaching within online higher education classrooms regardless of discipline. Gather.Town provides pedagogical benefits that other platforms, such as Microsoft Teams and Zoom, do not. Overall, its design facilitates meaningful and in-depth learning (Kim & Kim, 2023).

Gather.Town is especially useful for language learning (Fitria, 2021; Zhao & McClure, 2024). Zhao and McClure (2024) note that the customizable environment enables “teachers to pre-set a social scene (e.g., restaurants, hospitals, shopping malls) and create role-play scenarios for learners to practice their spoken language and social communication skills” (p. 243), which provides learning opportunities that are especially effective at helping students develop oral proficiency and communication skills.

Both instructors and students report that Gather.Town is a valuable platform for online classes, with curricula that emphasize group work, collaboration, class discussions, and peer-to-peer feedback (Lee et al., 2023; McClure & Williams, 2021). Ultimately, “online learning using [Gather] had positive effects on online-use skills and improved the efficacy of online learning, self-direction, and online interaction” (Kim & Kim, 2023).

Gather offers a “Gather Academy,” a robust selection of guided video tutorials and training that help instructors and learners set up their audio and video settings, navigate the virtual environment, integrate external tools, onboard other users, and customize the virtual classroom.

Effectiveness

When used to facilitate online learning, both students and teachers preferred Gather over platforms such as Microsoft Teams and Zoom (Lee et al., 2023; Latulipe & De Jaeger, 2022; McClure & Williams, 2021). Students reported that using Gather helped them learn practical skills more effectively than other forms of online learning, and 71% of those interviewed in one case study wanted to use the platform more often for distance learning (McClure & Williams, 2021). When compared to Zoom, students also noted that using Gather improved the ease of collaboration with classmates and the overall quality of teamwork, due to a sense of presence, belonging, and the feeling that they could more freely express their emotions with others (Lee et al., 2023). Additionally, students showed greater participation and social connectivity when using Gather than when using Zoom (Latulipe & De Jaeger, 2022). While 100% of educators in one case study found using Gather effective, they also unanimously agreed that it was not as effective as face-to-face instruction (McClure & Williams, 2021).

Potentially Problematic Aspects

Gather.Town's proximity chat feature requires users to have a stable internet connection and access to a device with a camera and a microphone. Additionally, given the gamified classroom environment with colorful 2D pixel art, users unfamiliar with digital games may struggle to use the platform effectively for learning.

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